

Effects of Plasma Surface Treatments on the Carbon/Epoxy Composite

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SUMMARY: Although the adhesive joint can distribute load over a larger area than the mechanical joint, requires no holes, adds very little weight to structures and has superior fatigue resistance, it requires careful surface preparation of adherends for reliable joining and less susceptibility to service environments. The load transmission capability of adhesive joints can be improved by increasing the surface free energy of adherends with surface treatments.

In this paper, two types of surface treatments such as the low pressure and the atmospheric pressure plasma surface treatments were performed to enhance the mechanical load transmission capabilities of carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joints. The suitable surface treatment conditions of carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joints for the low and the atmospheric pressure plasma systems were experimentally investigated with respect to gas flow rate, vacuum pressure, power intensity, and surface treatment time by measuring the surface free energies of specimens. The change of surface geometry of carbon/epoxy composite was measured with AFM (Atomic Force Microscopy) and the quantitative atomic concentration was determined with XPS (X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy) to investigate the failure modes of composite adhesive joints with respect to surface treatment time. From the AFM results, it was found that the surface of plasma treated carbon/epoxy composite was micro-roughened, which increased the load transmission capability. Also it was found that the ratio of oxygen concentration to carbon concentration of plasma treated carbon/epoxy composite surface was maximum at around 30 s treatment time and proportional to the load transmission capability of composite adhesive joint.

KEYWORDS: adhesive joint, surface treatment, low pressure plasma, atmospheric pressure plasma, contact angle, surface free energy, AFM, XPS

INTRODUCTION

The design of joints has become an important research area for composite structural components, because with a few exceptions, the strength of a structure is based on its joints, and not on its basic structure [1, 2]. There are two kinds of joints, namely mechanical and adhesive joints. A mechanical joint is usually created by fastening the adherends with bolts or rivets, while an adhesive joint uses an adhesive interlayer between the adherends. The adhesive joint has many advantages: it can distribute load over a larger area than the mechanical joint, requires no holes, adds very little weight to the structure and has superior fatigue resistance. However, the adhesive joint requires careful surface preparation of the adherends, is affected by service environments and is difficult to disassemble for inspection and repair [3, 4].

Some of the factors affecting adhesive joints are the surface treatment of adherends; the environmental temperature at which the adhesive joint is used; the residual thermal stresses generated due to the CTE (Coefficient of Thermal Expansion) differences between the adherends and the adhesive; and the geometry of the adherend [5].

Many researchers have investigated surface treatments of adhesive joints for improvement of

adhesion properties. Nihlstrand et al. [6] investigated microwave and radio-frequency glow-discharge plasmas for the lacquering of rubber-modified polypropylene plates with respect to the type of gas, plasma power and gas flow rate. Brennan et al. [7] studied the wettability of PEEK (poly ether ether ketone) using oxygen plasma surface treatment with respect to storage condition of PEEK material. Molina et al. [8] investigated the shrink-resistance and wetting properties of keratin fibers treated by glow discharge with air and nitrogen gases with respect to treatment time. Rhee et al. [9] studied the optimal volume ratio of acetylene and nitrogen gases and treatment time for the plasma surface treatment of aluminum-CFRP composite joint. Inagaki et al. [10] measured contact angles on Ar plasma treated polymeric films with respect to treatment time and analyzed the chemical composition of surfaces with XPS (X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy). Foerch et al. [11] analyzed the chemical composition of air plasma treated polyethylene materials with XPS. Wells et al. [12] investigated plasma oxidation of polystyrene and polyethylene with respect to plasma power and aging period. Ihara et al. [13] studied the tensile strength of glass fiber reinforced plastics, whose reinforcements were treated with NH_3 plasma. Qiu et al. [14, 15] treated nylon and polypropylene fabrics using He only and He + O_2 plasmas at atmospheric pressure. They investigated the surface chemical composition of the fibers by XPS and the morphology by SEM with respect to treatment time.

However, only a few studies [16] on the plasma surface treatments for carbon/epoxy composite has been carried out to improve the load transmission capabilities of carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joints.

In this study, two types of surface treatments such as the low and the atmospheric pressure plasma surface treatments were performed to enhance the load transmission capabilities of carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joints. The suitable surface treatment conditions for carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joints for low and atmospheric pressure plasma systems were experimentally investigated with respect to vacuum pressure, power intensity, and surface treatment time by measuring the surface free energies of specimens. The single lap shear tests and cleavage tests were performed using double cantilever beam adhesive joints and the results were related to the surface free energy of composite adherends. Finally, quantitative atomic concentrations were measured with XPS to relate the load transmission capabilities of carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joints to the surface treatment time.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: Carbon/epoxy composite prepregs (USN150, SK Chemicals, Korea) were used for the investigation of adhesion characteristics of the plasma surface treated carbon/epoxy composites.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of carbon/epoxy composite (USN150)

Longitudinal stiffness, E_1 (GPa)	131.6
Transverse stiffness, E_2 (GPa)	8.20
Shear stiffness, G_{12} (GPa)	4.5
Poisson ratio, ν_{12}	0.28
Density, ρ (kg/m^3)	1,560

Table 2. Mechanical properties of the epoxy adhesive (DP460)

Elastic stiffness, E (GPa)	2.7
Tensile strength, S (MPa)	45
CTE, α ($\mu\text{m/m}^\circ\text{C}$)	59
Poisson ratio, ν	0.4
Density, ρ (kg/m^3)	1,100

Table 3. Low pressure plasma surface treatment conditions

Main variable	Fixed conditions			
	Ar rate (sccm)	Pressure	Power	Time
Pressure (mTorr)	20	200-1000	100	30
Power (W)	20	500	10-170	30
Time (s)	20	500	100	10-1800

Table 4. Atmospheric pressure plasma surface treatment conditions

Main variable	Fixed conditions			
	Ar rate (ℓ/minute)	Power	Distance	Time
Power (W)	5	80-200	4	30
Distance (mm)	5	150	2-11	30
Time (s)	5	150	4	1-1800

Fig. 1 Cure cycle for the carbon/epoxy composite (USN150).

Fig. 2 Plasma surface treatment system for carbon/epoxy composites.

The carbon/epoxy composite prepreg was composed of polyacrylonitrile carbon fibers and DGEBA based epoxy resin. Carbon/epoxy composite specimens, with stacking sequence of $[0]_{10T}$, were fabricated using the cure cycle shown in Fig. 1. The mechanical properties of the composite specimens are listed in Table 1 [17]. The composite adherends were bonded with structural epoxy adhesive (DP460, 3M, USA), whose mechanical properties are listed in Table 2 [18]. The specimens were cured for 2.5 h at 80°C under a relative pressure of 0.6 MPa in an autoclave.

Plasma system: A plasma surface treatment system was designed for surface treatment of carbon/epoxy composite. It consisted of gas handling system, low pressure plasma reactor, atmospheric pressure plasma reactor, and power supply as shown in Fig. 2. The gas handling system consisted of high purity Ar gas (99.999 %) supply, Ar gas (99.9 %) supply, O₂ gas (99.9 %) supply, two mass flow controllers (1179A, MKS Instruments, USA) for 99.999 % Ar gas and 99.9 % O₂ gas in the range from 0 to 100 sccm (standard cubic centimeters per minute), a ball flow meter (FM-1050, Matheson, USA) for 99.9 % Ar gas in the range from 0 to 50 l/min, and 4 channel mass flow controller read-out box (GFC-104CH, Young Shin Engineering, Korea). The capacitively coupled low pressure plasma reactor chamber made of stainless steel had a reactive ion etching configuration inside, which had two parallel electrodes: grounded and powered electrodes. The diameter of the electrodes and the gap between them were 200 and 20 mm, respectively. The capacitively coupled atmospheric pressure plasma system had two parallel electrodes such as the grounded electrode coated with dielectric material (Al₂O₃) and the powered electrode, and the base plate coated with the same dielectric material. The area of the electrodes and the gap between them were 170 × 50 mm² and 1 mm, respectively. The distance between the electrodes and the base plate was adjustable. Atmospheric pressure plasma was generated between the two electrodes and diffused towards the base plate when the distance was less than 7 mm. The capacity and frequency of the power source were 300 W and 13.56 MHz (a radio-frequency), respectively and the output impedance was 50 Ω. A matching network system to maximize the efficiency of plasma generated in the reactors was employed.

Surface treatment: The low pressure plasma surface treatment of carbon/epoxy composite was performed with respect to the pressure in the reactor, the power supplied to the reactor, and the surface treatment time. The test ranges for each treatment variable are listed in Table 3. The atmospheric pressure plasma treatment was performed with respect to distance between the electrodes and the base plate, power intensity, and surface treatment time as listed in Table 4. Flow rate of Ar gas was fixed.

Surface free energy: The contact angles of liquid drops on the carbon/epoxy composite were measured with a contact angle meter (G-1, Erma, Japan) to calculate the surface free energy of the surface treated carbon/epoxy composite. The relationship between the contact angle and the surface free energy γ was expressed by the following equations [4]:

$$\gamma_{lg} (1 + \cos \theta) = 2\sqrt{\gamma_{sg}^d \gamma_{lg}^d} + 2\sqrt{\gamma_{sg}^p \gamma_{lg}^p} \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma = \gamma^d + \gamma^p \quad (2)$$

where subscripts s, l and g represent solid, liquid and gas, respectively, and superscripts p and d represent polar and dispersive components of surface free energy, respectively. The polar component γ_{sg}^p and the dispersive component γ_{sg}^d of the surface free energy of the carbon/epoxy composite were calculated using equation (1) with the measured contact angles of water and glycerol drops, whose surface free energies are already known as listed in Table 5. Then the surface free energy γ_{sg} of the carbon/epoxy composite was calculated using equation (2).

Single lap shear test: The effects of the plasma surface treatment of the carbon/epoxy composite on the adhesive joint strength were investigated by performing single lap shear tests on carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joints with an Instron static 4206 material testing system at the test speed of 1 mm/min. The thickness, width and length of composite adherend, whose stacking sequence was $[0]_{10T}$, were 1.4, 20 and 100 mm, respectively. The bond length and bond thickness of the single lap composite adhesive joint were 10 mm and 15 μm as shown in Fig. 3(a). The average shear strength S_s of the single lap carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joint was defined in this work as follows:

$$S_s = (\text{Load capability of the single lap joint}) / (\text{Bond area}) \quad (3)$$

Cleavage test: The effects of the plasma surface treatment of the carbon/epoxy composite on the adhesive joint strength were investigated by performing cleavage tests on double cantilever beam type carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joints with an Instron static 4206 material testing system at the test speed of 1 mm/min. The thickness, width and length of the composite adherend, whose stacking sequence was $[0]_{10T}$, were 1.4, 20 and 100 mm, respectively. The pre-crack length, bond length, and bond width of the double cantilever beam type carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joint were 45, 30 and 20 mm, respectively and the bond thickness was adjusted to 0.1 mm by inserting a thickness gauge between the adherends as shown in Fig. 3(b). The specimens were cured under the same conditions for single lap shear test specimens. The cleavage strength S_c of the carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joint was defined in this work as follows:

$$S_c = (\text{Load capability of the cleavage joint}) / (\text{Bond width}) \quad (4)$$

AFM study: AFM measurements were carried out in air at ambient temperature (20°C) with a NanoScope IIIa (Digital Instruments, USA). The experiments were carried out in the tapping mode with constant amplitude, using microfabricated cantilevers. The scanning was done using silicon nitride tip, square pyramid in shape, with a base dimension of approximately $4 \times 4 \mu\text{m}^2$. The characteristics of the probes were: spring constant, 20-100 N/m; resonant frequency, 290-330 kHz; cantilever length, 125 μm ; cantilever configuration, single beam. Scan size was $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$. All images contained 256 data points with the scan rate of 0.5 Hz.

Table 5. Surface free energies and their components for water and glycerol

Liquid	Surface free energy γ_{lg} (mJ/m ²)	Dispersive component γ_{lg}^d (mJ/m ²)	Polar component γ_{lg}^p (mJ/m ²)
water	72.8	21.8	51.0
glycerol	64.0	34.0	30.0

Fig. 3 Dimensions of carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joint specimen: (a) single lap shear test specimen; (b) cleavage test specimen (Units in mm).

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) study: SEM photographs of plasma surface treated carbon/epoxy composites were obtained in a XL30SFEG instrument (Phillips, The Netherlands) using an electron beam energy of 10 kV. The samples were coated with gold.

XPS study: XPS analysis was performed using ESCALAB MK II spectrometer (VG Scientific, UK), which irradiated the surfaces of plasma treated carbon/epoxy composite specimens with Mg K_α X-ray source (1253.6 eV) operating at 120 W (12 kV and 10 mA), to determine the chemical binding states and atomic concentration. The pressure inside the analysis chamber was 7×10⁻⁹ Pa. The measurements were made at a take-off angle of 0°. Survey scans were recorded in the range 0-1100 eV and high resolution scans were obtained for the C1s peaks.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Adhesion characteristics of low pressure plasma treated carbon/epoxy composites were investigated with respect to chamber pressure, power intensity, and treatment time as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4(a) shows the surface free energy γ_{sg} of the carbon/epoxy composite and the average shear strength S_s of the adhesive joint made of the surface treated carbon/epoxy composite with respect to the chamber pressure in the plasma reactor. The surface free energy and average shear strength were about 60 mJ/m² and 33 MPa, respectively in the pressure range of 400-800 mTorr, while lower than 60 mJ/m² at other pressures. Specially, the surface free energy and average shear strength were about 40 mJ/m² and 27 MPa, respectively, when the chamber pressure was lower than 300 mTorr, which was due to the lower ion impact density on the surface of the carbon/epoxy composite at the lower chamber pressure [19]. They were about 54 mJ/m² and 31 MPa, respectively, when the chamber pressure was higher than 800 mTorr because unstable plasmas were generated in this range.

Fig. 4(b) shows the surface free energy γ_{sg} of the carbon/epoxy composite and the average shear strength S_s of adhesive joint made of the surface treated carbon/epoxy composite with respect to the power supplied to the reactor. The surface free energy increased rapidly up to 65 mJ/m² at 30 W and decreased when the power supplied was higher than 30 W. The average shear strength was highest in the range of 10-30 W. The surface free energy and the average shear strength had similar trends with respect to the power supplied to the reactor. Also these results were similar to the results of water contact angle and peel strength from Nihlstrand et al. [6].

Fig. 4(c) shows the surface free energy γ_{sg} of the carbon/epoxy composite with respect to the surface treatment time. The surface free energy was 60 mJ/m² at 10 s and reached a peak value of 68 mJ/m² at 30 s, then decreased gradually after 30 s. The average shear strength S_s also had a maximum value of 29 MPa at 30 s.

The effects of adhesion characteristics of carbon/epoxy composites were investigated with respect to atmospheric pressure plasma surface treatment variables such as the distance between electrodes and base plate, power intensity and treatment time as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5(a) shows the surface free energy γ_{sg} of the carbon/epoxy composite and the average shear strength S_s of the adhesive joint made of the surface treated carbon/epoxy composite with respect to the distance between the electrodes and the base plate. The surface free energy and average shear strength increased gradually up to 83 mJ/m² and 42 MPa, respectively, when the distance was less than 7 mm. When the distance was larger than 9 mm, the surface free energy and average shear strength decreased abruptly because the atmospheric pressure plasma was generated only between two electrodes but not transferred to the base plate, which means that only activated radicals contributed the surface treatment. Therefore, the surface free energy and average shear strength had relatively low values about 60 mJ/m² and 30 MPa, respectively.

Fig. 5(b) shows the surface free energy γ_{sg} of the carbon/epoxy composite and the average shear strength S_s of adhesive joint made of the surface treated carbon/epoxy composite with respect to the power intensity. The surface free energy increased gradually up to 74 mJ/m² at 140 W and decreased when the power supplied was higher than 180 W. The average shear strength was 42 MPa, the highest value in the range of 120-140 W. The surface free energy and the average shear strength had similar trends with respect to the power supplied to the electrodes.

Fig. 4 Surface free energies of the carbon/epoxy composites and the average shear strengths of single lap adhesive joints composed of low pressure plasma surface treated carbon/epoxy composite adherends with respect to: (a) pressure in the reactor; (b) power of RF source; (c) surface treatment time.

Fig. 5 Surface free energies of the carbon/epoxy composites and the average shear strengths of single lap adhesive joints composed of atmospheric pressure plasma surface treated carbon/epoxy composite adherends with respect to: (a) distance between electrodes and base plate; (b) power of RF source; (c) surface treatment time.

Fig. 6 Maximum surface temperatures of carbon/epoxy composites during the plasma treatment.

Fig. 7 DMA test result for the glass transition temperature of the carbon/epoxy composite.

Fig. 5(c) shows the surface free energy γ_{sg} of the carbon/epoxy composite with respect to the surface treatment time. The surface free energy was 52 mJ/m^2 at 1 s and reached the peak value of 94 mJ/m^2 at 1 minute, then decreased gradually after 10 minutes. The average shear strength S_s also had the maximum value of 42 MPa at 1 minute.

The surface temperature of the carbon/epoxy composite increased up to 135°C with increasing surface treatment time during the low pressure plasma treatment as shown in Fig. 6, which thermally degraded the mechanical properties of the carbon/epoxy composite such as tensile modulus and

failure strength by 7 and 10 %, respectively, at 30 minutes [20] because the surface temperature approached the glass transition temperature of 155°C, which was measured by the DMA (Dynamic Mechanical Analysis) technique as shown in Fig. 7. While the surface temperature increased up to 160°C during the atmospheric pressure plasma treatment.

The surfaces of the atmospheric pressure plasma treated carbon/epoxy composites were scanned with the AFM equipment with respect to surface treatment time as shown in Fig. 8. The surface of the specimen before atmospheric plasma treatment had the average surface roughness of 11.6 nm, while the average surface roughnesses of the specimens with 30 s, 10 minute and 30 minute plasma treatment were 12.4, 14.1, and 20.3 nm, respectively.

The surfaces of atmospheric pressure plasma treated carbon epoxy composites were observed with SEM photographs with respect to treatment time as shown in Fig. 9. In short treatment time, carbon fibers were not observed on the specimen surface, while they were observed when the treatment time was above 10 minutes. The epoxy resin of carbon/epoxy composites was easily removed by ion impacts of atmospheric pressure plasma because of the low mechanical properties of resin, while the carbon fibers were not. The roughened surface with nano-size roughness by the short time plasma treatment less than 1 minute increased the bond area and mechanical interlocking of the adhesive joint, which might increase the joint strength of the specimen also [4]. However, the treatment time longer than 10 minutes caused the epoxy resin of the carbon/epoxy composite removed and degraded the mechanical properties of the composite.

Fig. 8 AFM images of atmospheric pressure plasma treated carbon/epoxy composites with respect to treatment time: (a) without treatment; (b) 30 s; (c) 10 minutes; (d) 30 minutes.

Fig. 9 SEM photographs of atmospheric pressure plasma treated carbon/epoxy composites with respect to treatment time ($\times 3000$): (a) without treatment; (b) 1 minute; (c) 10 minutes; (d) 30 minutes.

Fig. 10 Variation of O/C atomic ratio on the surface of plasma treated carbon/epoxy composite with respect to surface treatment time during: (a) low pressure plasma; (b) atmospheric pressure plasma.

Table 6. Atomic concentrations of the surface of low pressure plasma treated carbon/epoxy composite with respect to treatment time

Time (sec)	Atomic concentration (%)				
	F	O	N	C	Si
0	4.26	25.00	4.23	59.93	6.58
10	0.54	31.42	3.05	58.93	6.06
30	0.90	31.65	2.23	58.73	6.49
600	0.99	25.01	0.74	71.47	1.79
1800		25.84	3.53	63.61	7.02

Table 7. Atomic concentrations of the surface of atmospheric pressure plasma treated carbon/epoxy composite with respect to treatment time

Time (sec)	Atomic concentration (%)				
	F	O	N	C	Si
0	10.61	18.43	1.89	65.14	3.94
1	6.13	25.90	3.26	61.22	3.50
5	1.50	30.00	3.57	57.14	7.79
10	1.45	30.51	4.48	58.94	4.63
30	0.20	29.58	4.40	57.63	8.20
600	0.23	25.84	5.33	58.48	10.12
1800	0.52	22.01	8.97	65.48	3.02

Fig. 11 Failure modes of low pressure plasma treated carbon/epoxy composite single lap adhesive joints with surface treatment time: (a) without treatment; (b) 30 s; (c) 10 minutes.

The atomic concentrations of the carbon/epoxy composite surface are listed in Tables 6 and 7 with respect to treatment time. The major elements present in the plasma treated composite surfaces were carbon and oxygen, while small amounts of nitrogen, silicon and fluorine were also found on the composite surface as listed in Tables 6 and 7. The nitrogen originated from amine of the epoxy cross-linking agent [21]. Other elements such as fluorine and silicon were due to impurities. From the atomic concentrations of carbon/epoxy composites listed in Tables 6 and 7, it has been found that the oxygen concentrations increased in accordance with treatment time, while they decreased when the treatment time was higher than 10 minutes, at which the carbon concentrations relatively increased because of the increased amount of carbon fibers exposed on the composite surface from the removal of epoxy resin by ion impacts during plasma treatment. Fig. 10 shows the ratio of oxygen concentration to carbon concentration (O/C atomic ratio) of the specimen surfaces calculated from the atomic concentrations listed in Tables 6 and 7. The O/C atomic ratio increased rapidly and reached the peak value at around 10 s, then decreased after 10 minutes.

Fig. 12 Cleavage strength of plasma treated carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joint and the surface free energy of the composite with respect to the power of RF source during: (a) low pressure plasma; (b) atmospheric pressure plasma.

Fig. 13 Failure modes of plasma treated carbon/epoxy composite adhesive cleavage joints: (a) interfacial failure between the carbon/epoxy composite adherend and the epoxy adhesive when the plasma power was lower than 10 W; (b) cohesive failure in the epoxy adhesive when the plasma power was higher than 30 W.

All the plasma treated carbon/epoxy composite adhesive single lap joints failed with a partial bulk failure of composite adherend. Fig. 11 shows the failure modes of the low pressure plasma treated composite adhesive single lap joints. The extent of bulk failure of composite adherends of single lap adhesive joints increased as the surface free energy of composite adherend increased. The same phenomena were observed in the single lap shear tests of atmospheric pressure plasma treated composite adhesive joints also. However, the composite adhesive joints without surface treatment failed at the interface between the composite adherend and the adhesive layer without composite bulk failure. Therefore, it might be concluded that the mechanical load capability of the carbon/epoxy composite single lap adhesive joint was proportional to the O/C atomic ratio and the surface free energy of carbon/epoxy composite surface.

The cleavage strength S_c of low pressure plasma treated carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joints increased rapidly up to 6.6 kN/m at 30 W plasma power and saturated when the power was higher than 30 W as shown in Fig. 12(a), which was different from the lap shear test results shown in Fig. 4(b), in which the joint shear strength increased as the surface free energy increased, which was due to the change of failure mode of the cleavage joint from interfacial failure to cohesive failure in the adhesive as shown in Fig. 13 when the plasma power was 30 W. The cleavage strength of the carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joint was proportional to the surface free energy of the carbon/epoxy composite, because the failure mode was interfacial between the epoxy adhesive and the carbon/epoxy composite adherend when the applied power was lower than 10 W. When the power supplied was higher than 30 W, at which the carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joint failed cohesively in the epoxy adhesive layer, the cleavage strength of the adhesive joint was dependent on the mechanical strength of the epoxy adhesive because the adhesion strength between the epoxy adhesive and the composite adherend was higher than the strength of the epoxy adhesive due to the high surface free energy of the composite. The failure mode of the carbon/epoxy composite adhesive cleavage joint changed from the interfacial failure between the adhesive and the adherend to the cohesive failure in the adhesive at the surface free energy of about 40 mJ/m² as shown in Fig. 12(a). In the cleavage tests of the atmospheric pressure plasma treated composite adhesive joints, the cleavage strengths were constant in the whole test range and the failure modes were all cohesive failures of the epoxy adhesive because the surface free energies were larger than 65 mJ/m² in the range as shown in Fig. 12(b).

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, two types of surface treatments such as the low and the atmospheric pressure plasma surface treatments were performed to enhance the mechanical load transmission capabilities of carbon/epoxy composite adhesive joints. The surface free energies of the carbon/epoxy composite adherends were measured with respect to chamber pressure, power intensity, surface treatment time, and the distance between the electrodes and the base plate. The characteristics of the load capability of composite adhesive joints such as single lap joints and cleavage joints were related to surface free energies of the adherends. At a chamber pressure of 400 to 800 mTorr, the optimum power of the low pressure plasma surface treatment were 30 W when the surface treatment time was 30 s. The O/C atomic ratio of carbon/epoxy composite surface was proportional to the load transmission capabilities of carbon/epoxy composite single lap adhesive joints whose maximum value occurred when the

treatment time was 30 sec. With the distance of 4 to 7 mm between the electrodes and the base plate, the optimum power of the atmospheric pressure plasma treatment was in the range of 120 to 140 W when the treatment time was 1 minute. Also it was found that the double cantilever beam type cleavage joints composed of plasma treated composites all failed cohesively in the adhesive layer when the surface free energy of composite adherend was higher than 40 mJ/m² due to the high adhesion strength between the plasma treated composite surface and the adhesive.

REFERENCES

1. Hart-Smith, L.J. (1987). Joints. *Engineered Materials Handbook, Vol. 1, Composites*. Reinhart, T.J. (Ed.). Metals Park: ASM International, pp. 479-495.
2. Vinson, J.R. and Sierakowski, R.L. (1987). *The Behavior of Structures Composed of Composite Materials*. Dordrecht: Martinus Nijhoff, pp. 239-283.
3. Mallick, P.K. (1998). *Fiber-Reinforced Composites*. New York: Marcel Dekker, pp. 417-425.
4. Kinloch, A.J. (1987). *Adhesion and Adhesives*. London: Chapman & Hall, pp. 2-100.
5. Lee, D.G., Kim, J.K. and Cho, D.H. (1999). Effects of Adhesive Fillers on the Strength of Tubular Single Lap Adhesive Joints. *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **13**:1343-1360.
6. Nihlstrand, A., Hjertberg, T., Schreiber, H.P. and Klemberg-Sapieha, J.E. (1996). Plasma Treatment and Adhesion Properties of a Rubber-Modified Polypropylene. *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **10**:651-675.
7. Brennan, W.J., Feast, W.J., Munro, H.S. and Walker, S.A. (1990). Investigation of the Aging of Plasma Oxidized Peek. *Polymer*, **32**:1527-1530.
8. Molina, R., Jovancic, P., Comelles, F., Bertran, E. and Erra, P. (2002). Shrink-resistance and Wetting Properties of Keratin Fibres Treated by Glow Discharge. *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **16**:1469-1485.
9. Rhee, K.Y., Choi, N.S. and Park, S.J. (2002). Effect of Plasma Treatment of Aluminum on the Bonding Characteristics of Aluminum-CFRP Composite Joints. *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **16**:1487-1500.
10. Inagaki, N., Narushima, K., Tsutsui, Y. and Ohyama, Y. (2002). Surface Modification and Degradation of Poly (Lactic Acid) Films by Ar-plasma. *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **16**:1041-1054 (2002).
11. Foerch, R., Kill, G. and Walzak, M.J. (1993). Plasma Surface Modification of Polyethylene: Short Term vs. Long Term Plasma Treatment. *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **7**:1077-1089.
12. Wells, R.K., Badyal, J.P.S., Drummond, I.W., Robinson, K.S. and Street, F.J. (1993). Plasma Oxidation of Polystyrene vs. Polyethylene. *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **7**:1129-1137.
13. Ihara, T., Matsuoka, T. and Iriyama, Y. (1996). Fundamental Study on Fiber-Reinforced Epoxy Composites and Using Glass Fabric Treated by Low-Temperature Ammonia Plasma. *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **10**:823-832.
14. Qiu, Y., Zhang, C., Hwang, Y.J., Bures, B.L. and McCord, M. (2002). The Effect of Atmospheric Pressure Helium Plasma Treatment on the Surface and Mechanical Properties of Ultrahigh-Modulus Polyethylene Fibers. *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **16**:99-107.
15. Qiu, Y., Hwang, Y.J., Zhang, C., Bures, B.L. and McCord, M. (2002). Atmospheric Pressure Helium + Oxygen Plasma Treatment of Ultrahigh Modulus Polyethylene Fibers. *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **16**:449-457.
16. Kim, J.K. and Lee, D.G. (2002). Characteristics of Plasma Surface Treated Composite Adhesive Joints at High Environmental Temperature. *Composite Structures*, **57**:37-46.
17. Lee, C.S., Lee, D.G., Oh, J.H. and Kim, H.S. (2002). Composite Wrist Blocks for Double Arm Type Robots for Handling Large LCD Glass Panels. *Composite Structures*, **57**:345-355.
18. Kim, J.K. and Lee, D.G. (2001). Thermal Characteristics of Tubular Single Lap Adhesive Joints under Axial Loads. *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **15**:1511-1528.
19. Grill, A. (1994). *Cold Plasma in Materials Fabrication, from Fundamentals to Applications*. New York: IEEE, pp. 1-23.
20. Kim, J.K. and Lee, D.G. (2003). Adhesion Characteristics of Plasma Surface Treated Carbon/Epoxy Composite. *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology* (In-press).
21. Lee, H. and Neville, K. (1982). *Handbook of Epoxy Resins*. New York: McGraw-Hill, Chap. 7.